

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

SOCIAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN KAZAKHSTAN: PROBLEMS AND PERSPECTIVES

Aukenov Ye.

DBA Student

Almaty Management University

Almaty, Kazakhstan

Abstract

In 2021, Kazakhstan has introduced the first regulatory framework for the development of social entrepreneurship, which includes the definition, scope and objectives of social entrepreneurship as well as the measures of corresponding state support. Despite the fact that vast measures of state support were outlined in the legal acts only 25 social entrepreneurs have been added to the Register of Social Entrepreneurship so far. This article is aimed at analyzing the newly introduced legal framework in order to determine the barriers to the growth of social entrepreneurship and develop recommendations for the further improvement of state regulation of social entrepreneurship in Kazakhstan.

Keywords: social entrepreneurship, legal framework, measures of state support, Register of Social Entrepreneurship, problems and perspectives

Introduction. Over the past few decades, social entrepreneurs have become unprecedented drivers of social change in the most parts of the world. Being innovative and economically effective, they can contribute significantly to the achievement of important political and social goals, such as job creation, social inclusion, sustainable development and active civic participation. Many of them have been able to offer creative solutions to acute problems that previously could not be tackled neither by public authorities nor the private sector.

For Kazakhstan also, social entrepreneurship is not a new phenomenon. As noted by Pritvorova T.P., Gelashvili N.N. and Spanova B.K., despite the fact that for a long time there was no legislative consolidation of the concept of social entrepreneurship, certain empirical practices, that correspond to the widely accepted perception of social entrepreneurship, have still developed in different spheres [1].

In 2021, Kazakhstan has introduced the first regulatory framework for the development of social entrepreneurship, which includes the definition, scope and objectives of social entrepreneurship as well as the measures of corresponding state support.

This article is aimed at analyzing these legislative innovations in order to determine the barriers to the growth of social entrepreneurship and develop recommendations for the further improvement of state regulation of social entrepreneurship in Kazakhstan.

Legal Framework. The main legal act regulating social entrepreneurship in Kazakhstan is the Entrepreneurial Code. According to the Entrepreneurial Code, social entrepreneurs are defined as sole proprietors and legal entities (excluding large business enterprises) which are included in the Register of Social Entrepreneurship (Register) and correspond to one of the four categories summarized in Table 1 [2].

Table 1

Categories of Social Entrepreneurs

	First category	Second category	Third category	Fourth category
Main characteristics	Contribute to the employment of vulnerable groups of population	Promote the sale of goods, work or services manufactured, performed or rendered by vulnerable groups of population	Produce goods (perform work, provide services) aimed at creating equal opportunities for vulnerable groups of the population to participate in social activities	Carry out activities in specified areas
Vulnerable (disadvantaged) groups of population	1) persons with disabilities; 2) parents and other legal representatives raising a disabled child; 3) pensioners and citizens of pre-retirement age; 4) pupils and graduates of orphanages and boarding schools for orphans and children left without parental care (under the age of 29); 5) persons released from institutions of the penitentiary system (within twelve months after the release); 6) homeless persons; 7) parents and other legal representatives belonging to low-income, large (with four or more children) or single-parent families; 8) persons who have undergone medical and social rehabilitation from drug addiction or treatment of dependence on psychotropics (within twelve months after the rehabilitation or treatment); 9) repatriates.			N/A

<p>Areas of activities</p>	<p>Any</p>	<p>Any</p>	<p>1) social services aimed at maintaining everyday life; 2) medical services; 3) psychological services; 4) pedagogical services; 5) assistance in finding jobs and solving other problems related to labor adaptation; 6) increasing communication potential, rehabilitation and social adaptation, social support services; 7) production and (or) sale of medical equipment, prosthetic and orthopedic devices, software for digital healthcare, as well as technical means that can be used exclusively for the prevention of diseases, rehabilitation of disabled people, including medical habilitation of disabled children; 8) recreation of disabled persons and pensioners; 9) programs of additional education; 10) provision of access to social, transport and recreational infrastructure for disabled persons and persons with limited mobility.</p>	<p>1) psychological, pedagogical and other services aimed at strengthening the family institution, ensuring family upbringing of children and supporting motherhood and childhood; 2) recreation of children; 3) preschool education and training, primary, secondary, technical and vocational education; 4) psychological and pedagogical support for children with disabilities and students experiencing difficulties with the curricula of secondary education; 5) training of employees and volunteers of socially oriented non-profit organizations; 6) cultural and educational activities; 7) environmental protection; 8) geriatric and gerontological care, organization of health and longevity centers, healthy lifestyle events.</p>
<p>Financial and other requirements</p>	<p>1) at least 50% of employees must be from vulnerable groups of population; 2) at least 25% of labor costs should be used to pay salaries for vulnerable groups of population</p>	<p>1) at least 50% of the total income in the previous year must be generated from the sales of goods, work or services manufactured, performed or rendered by vulnerable groups of population; 2) at least 50% of net income in the previous year must be spent on the sales of goods, work or services manufactured, performed or rendered by vulnerable groups of population in the current year</p>	<p>1) at least 50% of the total income in the previous year must be generated from the areas of activities specified above; 2) at least 50% of net income in the previous year must be spent on areas of activities specified above in the current year</p>	<p>1) at least 50% of the total income in the previous year must be generated from the areas of activities specified above; 2) at least 50% of net income in the previous year must be spent on areas of activities specified above in the current year</p>

Source: compiled by the author based on the Entrepreneurial Code of Kazakhstan [2]

The Entrepreneurial Code also delineates the main objectives of social entrepreneurship (which mostly intersect the main characteristics of the categories of social entrepreneurs) and provides general guidelines on the structure and procedures of forming the Register [2].

A whole article in the Entrepreneurial Code is devoted to the measures of state support for social entrepreneurship. In particular, Article 232-1 outlines nine measures, such as ensuring the availability of infrastructure to support social entrepreneurship; tax benefits; financial support (including subsidies on the interest rates of bank loans and for paying property rent);

leasing state property on preferential terms; information support; consulting and methodological support, development through acceleration programs; assistance in the development of interregional cooperation and in the search for business partners; organization of vocational training and additional education; state grants for the implementation of significant social projects [2].

In addition to the Entrepreneurial Code, the Government of Kazakhstan has adopted a number of decrees (Table 2) which elaborate and lay out in detail all the procedures concerning social entrepreneurship, including the procedures and timelines for submitting and reviewing applications from potential social entrepreneurs, the regulations on the regional commissions that review the applications and make a final decision whether the applying organization should be included in the Register, and the measures of state support that social entrepreneurs are entitled to [3, 4, 5].

In brief, the Register is formed on an annual basis. In December, local authorities form the regional commissions and announce the start and end dates for accepting applications from the potential social entrepreneurs. Applications are accepted until the 10th of January and reviewed by the local authorities within two working days. Within five working days from the final date of accepting applications the regional commissions make a decision on organizations that are recommended to be included in the Register. The list of recommended organizations is then sent to the Ministry of National Economy, which forms the national Register for the current year and issues a corresponding Order not later than the 1st of February. Additional organizations can be included in the Register during the year on quarterly basis [3].

The regional commissions are formed by the decree of the local governor and include representatives of local state bodies, National Chamber of Entrepreneurs, nonprofit organizations and labour unions [4].

Table 2

The List of Government's Decrees Regulating Social Entrepreneurship

Decree	Issues Regulated
The Decree of the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan #773 adopted on October 28, 2021	Rules and procedures regarding the forming and maintaining of the Register (including the application procedures and timelines)
The Decree of the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan #778 adopted on October 29, 2021	Rules and regulations on regional commissions that review and make final decisions on applications from potential social entrepreneurs
The Decree of the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan #795 adopted on November 9, 2021	Rules for the implementation of state support measures for social entrepreneurs by state bodies, national holdings, national development institutions and other organizations
The Order of the Minister of National Economy #91 adopted on October 8, 2021	Rules for leasing the state property to social entrepreneurs on preferential terms

Source: compiled by the author based on the review of legal acts of Kazakhstan [3, 4]

Barriers to the Development of Social Entrepreneurship in Kazakhstan. Since the legal acts have been adopted less than a year ago and social entrepreneurship is just starting to develop, the data available at the moment is not sufficient to conduct a thorough analysis of the problems in this sphere. Nonetheless, several preliminary conclusions can be made.

Firstly, the major obstacle to the rapid development of social entrepreneurship in Kazakhstan is the absence of effective measures of government support.

The Entrepreneurial Code outlines nine measures of state support and presumes that these measures should be clarified and set out in detail in the government decree. However, the analysis of the Decree of the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan #795 adopted on November 9, 2021 has shown that six out of nine measures of state support are the same as for any other small and medium enterprises [5]. Thus, there are only three measures of state support specific for social entrepreneurs: the opportunity to lease state property on preferential terms, the reduction of taxable income by the amount of expenses spent on training employees from the vulnerable groups of population and the opportunity to pay the property tax at a rate of 0.5 percent of the tax base. Yet, even these measures have their limitations.

The rules for leasing state property to social entrepreneurs on preferential terms were approved by the Order of the Minister of National Economy #91 adopted on October 8, 2021 [6]. According to these rules, state property is leased to social entrepreneurs on tender basis and the lender sets out the list of documents that social entrepreneurs have to submit in order to participate in the tender. Hence, social entrepreneurs have to register on a special website and submit a new list of documents, which is rather burdensome considering that they have already collected and submitted a long list of documents to become a social entrepreneur in the first place. Moreover, according to the rules, to participate in the tender social entrepreneurs are expected to pay a guarantee fee. Taking into account that most social entrepreneurs work at a margin and do not have cash surplus, this requirement can become a serious barrier for them to get state property for lease on preferential terms.

The other two measures of state support (regarding the tax benefits) are mentioned in the legal acts as specific for social entrepreneurs. However, a deeper review of these norms [7] shows that similar tax benefits are also available for other groups of taxpayers such as sole proprietors, legal entities applying a special tax regime based on a simplified declaration, subsoil users

training local staff, organizations operating in the social sphere, etc.

Therefore, it can be concluded that state support measures available for social entrepreneurs at the moment are insufficient and do not encourage social entrepreneurs to apply for the Register.

Secondly, the list of documents that potential social entrepreneurs have to submit in order to be included in the Register is rather demanding, time-consuming and implies bureaucratic burdens on applicants. For instance, in order to be included to the first category of social entrepreneurs, potential applicants have to submit:

- 1) a copy of the applicant's staff list, valid on the date of application;
- 2) copies of employment contracts with the applicant's employees from among the vulnerable groups of population;
- 3) copies of documents confirming that the applicant's employees are classified as vulnerable groups of population;
- 4) information on the number and wages of the applicant's employees;
- 5) copies of consents to the processing of personal data of the applicant's employees from among the vulnerable groups of population [3].

The list of documents confirming that the applicant's employees are classified as vulnerable groups of population includes such personal documents as convict's personal file (dossier) and characteristics from the local police officer for persons released from institutions of the penitentiary system, medical reports for persons who have undergone medical and social rehabilitation from drug addiction or treatment of dependence on psychotropics, etc.

Thus, the list of documents is not only burdensome, but also includes personal information that most people would not be willing to share either with employers or with government officials and regional commission members. Moreover, the adopted legal acts do not include any guarantees of confidentiality or responsibility of state officials and regional commission members for a disclosure of personal records.

As for the second, third and fourth categories, it is required that applicants fill out special forms regarding their financial operations (to confirm that at least 50 percent of the total income in the previous year was generated from the specified areas of activities and at least 50 percent of net income in the previous year was spent on specified areas of activities), whereas this information could be automatically confirmed by local tax authorities.

Thirdly, low level of activity of state bodies and scarcity of information available has resulted in the lack of interest from potential social entrepreneurs [7, 8]. Mostly, publications on the official websites of state bodies refer to the legal acts and do not provide detailed practical explanation of rules and procedures. The websites of state authorities do not even include information on how and where social entrepreneurs can get assistance on application procedures.

Furthermore, in accordance with the adopted legal acts, the first call for applications was supposed to be

announced by the local authorities in December 2021 with the deadline for submitting applications set by January 10, 2022. However, the monitoring of the official websites of regional state bodies, where the announcements should have been published, has educed that only seven out of seventeen regions published their announcements and accepted the applications on time [9-15]. Four regions set different application periods than those stipulated by the government decree [16-19]; and six regions did not accept applications at all [20-25].

These violations of time frames set by the legal acts can be explained by two factors. Firstly, on January 5, 2022 the president of Kazakhstan declared a two-week state of emergency throughout the territory of Kazakhstan after mass unrest had broken out in the country. During this period of time the Internet as well as other means of communication were shut down or worked with interruptions. Secondly, the main government decrees that clarify the rules and time frames for accepting applications were adopted in late October 2021, which left very limited time for both local authorities and the potential social entrepreneurs to prepare for the application period.

As a result, the first Register, formed by the Order of the Minister of National Economy on January 29, 2022, included only two social entrepreneurs, both from Karaganda region.

The second call for applications was announced in February 15, 2022 with the application period lasting from March 1 till March 15, 2022. Consequently, 23 more social entrepreneurs were added to the Register in April 2022.

As of May, 2022 Kazakhstan's Register includes only 25 social entrepreneurs [26]. For comparison, the European Commission estimates that Italy has 102,461 social enterprises, Germany has 77,459 social enterprises, the United Kingdom has 30,753 social enterprises, etc. [27]. In Russia, where similar regulations were adopted only in 2019, there are already more than 6,000 registered social entrepreneurs [28].

Perspectives for Kazakhstan. According to Kazakhstan's Bureau of National Statistics [29] there are more than 90,000 small and medium sized enterprises operating in the areas of activities specified for social entrepreneurs. Pritvorova T.P., Gelashvili N.N., and Spanova B.K. also estimate that there are almost 3,000 non-governmental organizations that could be considered as social enterprises [1]. Hence, there is significant potential for the growth of social entrepreneurship in Kazakhstan given that the abovementioned problems are tackled. Some of the measures that could help to overcome the highlighted barriers and encourage the active development of social entrepreneurship in Kazakhstan are outlined below.

First. One of the most effective ways to jump-start the development of social entrepreneurship could be **tailoring the measures of state support**. In particular, it is recommended to adopt a unified national program with well-defined and realistic measures of state support. A good example of such a program is Kazakhstan's "Business Road Map" which has been implemented since 2010 in order to support small and medium enterprises. The national program for the

development of social entrepreneurship should include financial measures of state support that are most needed by social entrepreneurs: subsidizing interest rates on bank loans, issuing guarantee letters for social entrepreneurs who do not have enough collateral to get a bank loan, subsidizing lease payments for premises, giving privileges in the tenders of state bodies, providing public contracts, etc.

Second. Automation and digitalization of the application procedures could stimulate more social entrepreneurs to apply for the Register. This could be reached by integrating the databases of central and local state authorities which would simplify and shorten the list of documents that potential social entrepreneurs have to submit. For instance, in order to prove the employment of persons from vulnerable groups of population potential social entrepreneurs have to request certificates confirming the fact of disability, personal records and characteristics from local police officers for persons released from penitentiary system institutions, medical reports for persons who have undergone medical and social rehabilitation from drug addiction, copies of birth certificates and certificates confirming the fact of child's disability for parents of disabled children, etc. All of these documents are issued by state authorities and are available at their databases. Thus, integrating the information systems of state bodies could simplify the application procedures, lessen the burden on social entrepreneurs and restrict the access to personal information.

Third. Active promotion of social entrepreneurship via mass media and social networks can raise awareness and motivate more organizations to apply. Moreover, state authorities should **publish detailed instructions and guidelines on application procedures** with FAQ and contact information on their official websites. In the ideal case, local authorities should set up **regional hubs or centers of assistance for social entrepreneurs** that can provide all the necessary support and service for social entrepreneurs.

The implementation of these recommendations can boost the development of social entrepreneurship and help the government address the most critical social problems.

REFERENCES:

1. Pritvorova T.P., Gelashvili N.N., Spanova B.K. Social entrepreneurship institutional support: world practice and opportunities Kazakhstan. *Economics: the strategy and practice*. 2020; 15(1): 71-87. (In Russian). URL: <https://esp.ieconom.kz/jour/article/view/163/159>
2. The Entrepreneurial Code of Kazakhstan (articles 79-1, 79-2, 79-3, 79-4, 232-1). URL: <https://adilet.zan.kz/rus/docs/K1500000375#z2078> [Date accessed: May 16, 2022]
3. The Decree of the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan #773 adopted on October 28, 2021. URL: <https://adilet.zan.kz/rus/docs/P2100000773> [Date accessed: May 16, 2022]
4. The Decree of the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan #778 adopted on October 29, 2021.

URL: <https://adilet.zan.kz/rus/docs/P2100000778> [Date accessed: May 16, 2022]

5. The Decree of the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan #795 adopted on November 9, 2021. URL: <https://adilet.zan.kz/rus/docs/P2100000795> [Date accessed: May 16, 2022]

6. The Order of the Minister of National Economy #91 adopted on October 8, 2021. URL: <https://adilet.zan.kz/rus/docs/V2100024750> [Date accessed: May 16, 2022]

7. Official website of the National Chamber of Entrepreneurs of the Republic of Kazakhstan. Aliya Umirzakova: I am a 100% Social Entrepreneur. (In Russian). URL: <https://atameken.kz/ru/news/47106-aliya-umirzakova-ya-na-00--social-nyj-predprinimatel>

8. What Kazakhstanis Know about Social Entrepreneurship? (In Russian). URL: <https://kapital.kz/business/63113/chto-kazakhstantsy-znayut-o-sotsial-nom-predprinimatel-stve.html>

9. Official Website of the Department of Entrepreneurship and Tourism of Akmola region. URL: <https://www.gov.kz/memleket/entities/aqmola-upp/press?lang=ru> [Date accessed: May 17, 2022]

10. Official Website of the Department of Entrepreneurship of Aktobe region. URL: <https://www.gov.kz/memleket/entities/aktobe-kasipkerlik/press/news/1?lang=ru> [Date accessed: May 17, 2022]

11. Official Website of the Department of Entrepreneurship and Industrial-Innovative Development of Almaty region. URL: <https://www.gov.kz/memleket/entities/zhetysu-kasipkerlik/press/news/1?lang=ru> [Date accessed: May 17, 2022]

12. Official Website of the Department of Entrepreneurship and Industrial-Innovative Development of Atyrau region. URL: <https://www.gov.kz/memleket/entities/atyrau/press/news/1?lang=ru> [Date accessed: May 17, 2022]

13. Official Website of the Department of Entrepreneurship of Karaganda region. URL: <https://www.gov.kz/memleket/entities/karaganda-kasipkerlik/press/news/1?lang=ru> [Date accessed: May 17, 2022]

14. Official Website of the Department of Entrepreneurship and Industrial-Innovative Development of Pavlodar region. URL: <https://www.gov.kz/memleket/entities/pavlodar-uuir/press/news/1?lang=ru> [Date accessed: May 17, 2022]

15. Official Website of the Department of Entrepreneurship and Industrial-Innovative Development of North Kazakhstan region. URL: <https://www.gov.kz/memleket/entities/sko-kasipker/press/news/1?lang=ru> [Date accessed: May 17, 2022]

16. Official Website of the Department of Entrepreneurship and Industrial-Innovative Development of West Kazakhstan region. URL: <https://www.gov.kz/memleket/entities/bko-kasipkerlik/press/news/1?lang=ru> [Date accessed: May 17, 2022]

17. Official Website of the Department of Entrepreneurship and Industrial-Innovative Development of

Zhambyl region. URL: <https://www.gov.kz/memleket/entities/zhambyl-kasipkerlik/press/news/details/325184?lang=ru> [Date accessed: May 17, 2022]

18. Official Website of the Department of Entrepreneurship and Trade of Mangystau region. URL: <https://www.gov.kz/memleket/entities/mangystau-upp/press/news/1?lang=ru> [Date accessed: May 17, 2022]

19. Official Website of the Department of Entrepreneurship and Industrial-Innovative Development of East Kazakhstan region. URL: <https://www.gov.kz/memleket/entities/vko-kasipkerlik/press/news/1?lang=ru> [Date accessed: May 17, 2022]

20. Official Website of the Department of Entrepreneurship and Industrial-Innovative Development of Kostanay region. URL: <https://www.gov.kz/memleket/entities/kostanai-kasipkerlik-industiya-innovatsiya/press/news/1?lang=ru> [Date accessed: May 17, 2022]

21. Official Website of the Department of Entrepreneurship and Tourism of Kyzylorda region. URL: <https://www.gov.kz/memleket/entities/kyzylorda-tourism/press/news/1?lang=ru> [Date accessed: May 17, 2022]

22. Official Website of the Department of Entrepreneurship and Trade of Turkestan region. URL: <https://www.gov.kz/memleket/entities/turkestan-kasipkerlik-sauda/press/news/1?lang=ru> [Date accessed: May 17, 2022]

23. Official Website of the Department for Investments and the Development of Entrepreneurship of Nur-Sultan city. URL: <https://www.gov.kz/memleket/entities/nur-sultan-uir/press/news/1?lang=ru> [Date accessed: May 17, 2022]

24. Official Website of the Department of Entrepreneurship and Investments of Almaty city. URL: <https://www.gov.kz/memleket/entities/almaty-upp/press/news/1?lang=ru> [Date accessed: May 17, 2022]

25. Official Website of the Department of Entrepreneurship and Industrial-Innovative Development of Shymkent city. URL: <https://www.gov.kz/memleket/entities/shymkent-kasipkerlik/press/news/1?lang=ru> [Date accessed: May 17, 2022]

26. Official Website of the Ministry of National Economy of the Republic of Kazakhstan. URL: <https://www.gov.kz/memleket/entities/economy/documents/details/299951?directionId=203&lang=ru> [Date accessed: May 18, 2022].

27. European Commission (2020). Social enterprises and their ecosystems in Europe. Comparative synthesis report. Authors: Carlo Borzaga, Giulia Galera, Barbara Franchini, Stefania Chiomento, Rocío Nogales and Chiara Carini. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. URL: <https://europa.eu/!Qq64ny>

28. The Foundation of Regional Social Programs “Our Future”. The Number of Social Entrepreneurs is Rapidly Growing in Russia: “Our Future” Foundation Summed up the Results. URL: <https://www.nb-fund.ru/press-center/news/v-rossii-stremitelno-rastet-chislo-sotsialnykh-predprinimateley/>

29. Bureau of National Statistics of the Republic of Kazakhstan. Small and Medium Enterprises in the Republic of Kazakhstan Yearbook. URL: <https://stat.gov.kz/official/industry/139/publication>